

JOB SATISFACTION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS WITH REGARD TO MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION AND MONTHLY INCOME

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this research was identified the significant difference of secondary school teachers' job satisfaction with regard to medium of instruction and monthly income. The research has been designed with the survey model. In the research, Job Satisfaction Scale (JSS) was used to collect data. The present study has been carried out among secondary school teachers at Kovilpatti Taluk of Thoothukudi district. The investigator found that there is significant difference among Tamil and English medium secondary school teachers in their job satisfaction and also there is significant association between monthly income and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

Keyword: - Job Satisfaction, Secondary School Teachers, Medium of Instruction

1. INTRODUCTION

Job Satisfaction may be defined as pleasurable and or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences. Spector (1997) offered three reasons to clarify the importance of job satisfaction: (a) high level of job satisfaction can be a sign of emotional wellness and mental fitness, (b) organizations can adopt a utilitarian perspective in which employee behavior can be expected to influence organizational operations according to the level employee satisfaction / dissatisfaction, (c) job satisfaction can be an indicator of effective organizational operations[1]. Job satisfaction is the degree to which people like their jobs. Some people work and find it to be a central part of life. Others hate work and do so only because they must. Job satisfaction is to some extent a reflection of good treatment. It can also be considered an indicator of emotional well-being or psychological health. Job satisfaction is simply how people feel about their jobs. Job satisfaction can be considered as a global feeling about the job related constellation of attitudes about various aspects or facets of the global approach is used when the overall or bottom line attitude is of interest[2]. In this era of rapid technological change, successful institutions must have teachers who are open to innovation and to changing roles, and are able to work together productively. Research shows that teachers most likely to be adaptable, cooperative, and productive are those who are satisfied with their jobs. Job Satisfaction dispels the notion that job stress necessarily leads to dissatisfaction, and shows how an organization should focus on increasing satisfaction rather than just reducing stress. It is especially important for management to stimulate job satisfaction by improving their employees' sense of achievement through making tasks and their objectives clear, as well as giving feedback[3].

2. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Every profession has got certain aspects conducive for job satisfaction. At the same time it has other aspects that leads to dissatisfaction. Teaching profession is not an exception. If it is possible to isolate the factors of dissatisfaction, attempts can be made either to change the dissatisfying conditions or to reduce their intensity so as to increase the holding power of the profession. There is no gainsaying the fact that unless the teacher is satisfied with his occupation, he cannot deliver the good satisfactory. (Ramakrishnaiah) Job satisfaction is a primary requisite for

any successful teaching learning process. Job satisfaction is a complex phenomenon involving various personal, institutional and social aspects. If the teachers attain adequate job satisfaction, they will be in a position to fulfil the educational objectives and national goals. True enough, it is said that a large number of teachers of the present day have no interest in their profession but they continue in the profession only as mechanical wage earners [4]. Though, several factors influence the job satisfaction of higher secondary teachers, the investigator study only the influence of medium of instruction and teachers' monthly income on job satisfaction of higher secondary teachers in the present study. So this study limited to the background variables namely, medium of instruction and teachers monthly income. Thus the present study is designed to analyze the job satisfaction of teachers with regard to medium of instruction and teachers' monthly income.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To find out whether there is any significant difference between Tamil medium and English medium secondary school teachers in their job satisfaction.
- To find out whether there is any significant association between monthly income and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

3. HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

- There is no significant difference between Tamil medium and English medium secondary school teachers in their job satisfaction.
- There is no significant association between monthly income and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

4. METHODOLOGY AND INSTRUMENTATION

The research has been designed with the survey model. In the research, Job Satisfaction Scale (JSS) was used to collect data. The present study has been carried out among secondary school teachers at Kovilpatti Taluk of Thoothukudi district. The investigator used t-test and Chi-square test for analyzing the collected data.

5. ANALYSIS OF DATA

Null Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between Tamil medium and English medium secondary school teachers in their job satisfaction.

Table – 1: t-test showing the significant difference between Tamil and English medium secondary school teachers in their job satisfaction

Medium of Instruction	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
Tamil	95	133.33	17.668	2.313	S*
English	105	134.12	16.926		

* Significant at 5% level of significance

It is inferred from the above table that calculated 't' value (2.313) is greater than the table value (1.96) for df 198 at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It shows that there is significant difference among Tamil and English medium secondary school teachers in their job satisfaction. While comparing the mean scores of Tamil (133.33) and English (134.12) medium secondary school teachers, the English medium secondary school teachers have better job satisfaction than the Tamil medium teachers.

Null Hypothesis 2: There is no significant association between monthly income and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

Table 2: Chi-square test showing Significant Association between monthly income and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers

Monthly Income (Rs.)	Low		Moderate		High		Calculated value of χ^2	Remarks at 5% level
	O	E	O	E	O	E		
Below Rs. 20000	14	17.1	93	82.6	7	13.7	12.684	S*
Rs.20000-30000	6	5.4	22	25.4	7	4.2		
Above Rs.30000	11	7.9	30	37.0	10	6.1		

* Significant at 5% level of significance

It is inferred from the above table that calculated ' χ^2 ' value (12.684) is greater than the table value (9.49) for df 4 at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It shows that there is significant association between monthly income and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

6. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

- There is significant difference among Tamil and English medium secondary school teachers in their job satisfaction. And also the English medium secondary school teachers have better job satisfaction than the Tamil medium teachers.
- There is significant association between monthly income and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

7. CONCLUSION

The investigator found that there is significant association between monthly income and job satisfaction of secondary school teachers. And also, the investigator found that the English medium secondary school teachers have better job satisfaction than the Tamil medium secondary school teachers. Thus, the study concluded that medium of instruction and income of teachers in enhancing job satisfaction is very important. A better understanding of the causes for job satisfaction / dissatisfaction is desirable not because it will enable us to make them completely satisfied, but because it may help the administrators to relieve that intense and painful dissatisfaction which injures both the individual and the society in which he lives[4].

8. REFERENCES

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BIOGRAPHIES

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